

UVLF Robustness Report (GV, Island1, IslandB)

Robustness diagnostics recomputed from the latest MCMC chains (English-only labels).

Grand Valley

Samples used	20,000
# Parameters	6
Scaler	robust
K* (GMM, BIC)	4 (full)
BIC(K*)	192134.5
Multimodal marginals	6
LLmax	-227.9
AIC	467.8
BIC	476.3
$\Delta \ln Z$ (median)	-3.04
$\Delta \ln Z$ IQR	0.00
Bootstrap K (mode)	4
Bootstrap K (mean \pm std)	4.00 \pm 0.00

Posterior corner plot.

GMM clusters (selected K and covariance family).

Log-likelihood distribution.

Bootstrap distribution of K

Bootstrap distribution of selected K.

Island-1

Samples used	20,000
# Parameters	6
Scaler	robust
K* (GMM, BIC)	4 (full)
BIC(K*)	205327.2
Multimodal marginals	3
LLmax	-89.1
AIC	190.3
BIC	198.7
$\Delta \ln Z$ (median)	-1.02
$\Delta \ln Z$ IQR	0.00
Bootstrap K (mode)	4
Bootstrap K (mean \pm std)	4.00 \pm 0.00

Posterior corner plot.

GMM clusters (selected K and covariance family).

Log-likelihood distribution.

Bootstrap distribution of K

Bootstrap distribution of selected K.

Island-2

Samples used	20,000
# Parameters	6
Scaler	robust
K* (GMM, BIC)	4 (full)
BIC(K*)	181610.2
Multimodal marginals	6
LLmax	-89.2
AIC	190.3
BIC	198.7
$\Delta \ln Z$ (median)	-0.70
$\Delta \ln Z$ IQR	0.00
Bootstrap K (mode)	4
Bootstrap K (mean \pm std)	4.00 \pm 0.00

Posterior corner plot.

GMM clusters (selected K and covariance family).

Log-likelihood distribution.

Bootstrap distribution of K

Bootstrap distribution of selected K.

Cross-run comparison

Run	K* (BIC)	Cov	$\Delta \ln Z$ (med)	IQR	AIC	BIC	K_boot (mode)	mean \pm std
GV	4	full	-3.04	0.00	467.8	476.3	4	4.00 \pm 0.00
Island1	4	full	-1.02	0.00	190.3	198.7	4	4.00 \pm 0.00
IslandB	4	full	-0.70	0.00	190.3	198.7	4	4.00 \pm 0.00